

Evaluation of the Outcome of the Middle Turbinate Medialization (Fixation to Nasal Septum) by Various Surgical Technique

Ali Jameel Alhaideri ✉

Ministry of Health, Al-Imamain Al-Kadhmain Teaching Hospital, Baghdad, Iraq

Jaafer Mohammed Kadhim Al-Hassani

College of Medicine, Al-Nabrain University, Baghdad, Iraq

Zeena Jamal Alkhazraji

Medical Technical Institute Al-Mansur, Middle Technical University, Baghdad, Iraq

Suggested Citation

Alhaideri, A.J., Al-Hassani, J.M.K., & Alkhazraji, Z.J. (2024).

Evaluation of the Outcome of the Middle Turbinate Medialization (Fixation to Nasal Septum) by Various Surgical Technique.

European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences, 2(6), 1019-1029.

DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(6\).89](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(6).89)

Abstract:

The primary objectives and essential aspects of ESS are to facilitate the proper drainage and ventilation of the afflicted groups of paranasal sinuses. The size and location of the middle turbinate directly impact the drainage of all paranasal sinuses.

A prospective study has been conducted in the otolaryngology department at Al-Imamain Al-kadhmain teaching hospital from September 2021 to May 2023 on 180 selected patients, divided into three groups; each contains sixty patients with the following specific surgical intervention: group I: medialization of the middle turbinate only, group II: medialization of the middle turbinate with fixation to

the nasal septum, and group III: medialization of the middle turbinate with fixation to the nasal septum by trans-septal sutures. Postoperatively, follow-up was done weekly during the 1st month and every 2 weeks during the 2nd month by assessing symptom improvement and nasal endoscopic findings. The findings showed that one hundred (55.6%) patients were males and eighty (44.4%) patients were females. The patients' ages varied from 20 to 48 years (mean \pm SD = (33.45 \pm 8.95) years). Post-operative improvement of presenting symptoms in order of sequence from higher to lower were as follows: nasal obstructions (74%), nasal discharge (74%), facial pain (70%), smell disorders (61%), and headache (53%).

The current study concluded that the technique of middle turbinate medialization promotes effective drainage and ventilation, allowing for long-term monitoring and post-surgical suction clearing. Although it has its limits, the suturing method of the middle turbinate (conchopexy) is an efficient technique for preventing lateralization of the middle turbinate. This method has demonstrated superior overall outcomes when compared to iatrogenic adhesion (Bolgerization).

Keywords: Middle turbinate medialization, Nasal septum, ESS.

Introduction

Cilia propel mucus with a velocity ranging from 3 to 25 mm/min towards the natural sinus ostia, and finally to the nasopharynx and oropharynx,

where the carried mucus is ingested. The flow pattern is unique to each sinus and will continue to exist even if surgical procedures are performed to establish alternate openings in the sinus. Consequently, FESS has been widely

accepted due to its ability to restore the drainage of the sinuses by utilizing their natural drainage channels (Lal and Stankiewicz, 2010).

On the front and central sides, the middle turbinate envelops the ethmoidal infundibulum, including the bulla ethmoidalis and the uncinate process. Consequently, the development of chronic and recurrent sinusitis may be influenced by pathological conditions that include "a hypertrophied middle turbinate, a paradoxical middle turbinate, a middle turbinate concha bullosa, a duplicated middle turbinate, and a floppy middle turbinate." This is due to the abnormal middle turbinate mechanically obstructing the osteomeatal complex, necessitating surgical intervention (Banfield and McCombe, 1999). Sinusitis recurrence rate after middle meatal endoscopic surgery may be significantly affected by a normal middle turbinate (Hewitt and Orlandi, 2008).

There is a high probability of postoperative lateralization of the middle turbinate and reobstruction of drainage at the middle meatus when endoscopic surgery involves fracturing the middle turbinate to reach the middle meatus. It has been shown, however, that the middle meatus may remain insufficiently open after surgery, even after delicately adjusting the middle turbinate so as not to fracture it. The middle turbinate's size or the presence of adhesions between it and the lateral nasal wall are two potential causes of this. Manipulating the normal middle turbinate to maintain the middle meatus open is an essential step in middle meatal endoscopic surgery (Chen et al. 2015).

Present methods for medialization of the MT encompass the utilization of pacers and packing, deliberate induction of scarring in the MT and neighboring septum (bolgarization), and the act of suturing the MT to the septum. A novel method has been developed that enables the placement of a minuscule biodegradable implant, which secures the MT to the septum (Hegazy et al. 2015). The primary objectives and essential aspects of ESS are ensuring adequate drainage and ventilation for the affected paranasal sinus group. The size and position of the middle turbinate directly impact the drainage

of all paranasal sinuses. This is due to its connection to the sphenoethmoidal recess and the osteomeatal complex. Consequently, fixing the middle turbinate is the most important step for a successful endoscopic sinus surgery (ESS) (Weitzel and Wormald, 2008). The current study aims to evaluate the effect of medializing the middle turbinate following endoscopic sinus surgery on middle meatus patency, both with and without fixation to the nasal septum.

Materials and Methods

Patients and Study Design

A prospective study was done in the otolaryngology department at Al-Imamain Al-Kadhmain Teaching Hospital from September 2021 to March 2023 on 180 patients. The patients were split into three groups of 60, with each group receiving a different surgical procedure: group I received medialization of the middle turbinate only; group II received medialization of the middle turbinate with fixation to the nasal septum by creating iatrogenic adhesion; and group III received medialization of the middle turbinate with fixation to the nasal septum by transseptal sutures.

Inclusion Criteria

All adults patients (age >18 years old, primary and revision surgery, and refractory chronic rhinosinusitis that cannot be treated medically).

Exclusion Criteria

Sinonasal malignancy, immunocompromised patients, and middle turbinate abnormality such as (concha bullosa, paradoxical, and previous partial resection).

Technique of Nasal Endoscopic Examination

- Explanation of the procedure to the patient.
- Sitting position of the patient with equipment preparation.
- Local anesthesia was used by applying (lidocaine 2% + oxymetazolin 0.1%) nasal spray

and the endoscopy was started after 5-10 minutes.

- An organized nasal endoscopy was performed utilizing a 0° and 300 rigid Hopkins rod endoscope, allowing for a comprehensive and detailed examination. The examination was conducted in three passes to ensure thoroughness.
- The preliminary passage occurs along the nasal floor. An initial assessment should be conducted to evaluate the condition of the sinonasal mucosa, alterations during decongestion, and the general architecture of the sinonasal cavity. The inferior meatus is the first region to examine. Following the assessment of the inferior meatus, the lower section of the inferior turbinate and the nasal septum were evaluated. The nasopharynx is reached when the scope has been moved into the nasal cavity. The whole nasopharynx, including the openings of the Eustachian tubes, the torus tubarius, the fossa of Rosenmuller, and the adenoid pad (if present) were visible.
- The endoscope is reinserted between the middle and inferior turbinate during the second pass. During the examination, the lower section of the middle turbinate and middle meatus, as well as the fontanelles and any extra holes in the maxillary sinus, are viewed while going towards the back.
- The third pass takes place during the removal of the endoscope. Accessing the deeper regions of the middle meatus requires lateral rotation of the scope beneath the posterior part of the middle turbinate.
- CT scans were performed on all patients to assist in our diagnosis and provide a surgical roadmap for the nose and paranasal sinuses.
- Patients prepared well and investigation done for fitness for general anesthesia.

Surgical Technique

- A nasal pledge of local nasal decongestant (2ml of xylometazolin 0.1%), was put inside the nose near the middle meatus 10-20 minutes before the operation started.
- Then under general anesthesia with endotracheal tube (orotracheal tube) and reverse Trendelenburg position.
- Endoscopic examination of the nose and post-nasal space done by 3 passes using the 00 rigid scope.
- If there was septal deviation obstructing the access to the osteomeatal complex, septoplasty was done first or endoscopic surgery was initiated in the patent side followed by septoplasty.
- Initially, the middle turbinate was medialized utilizing a freer elevator to locate the uncinat process. The standard steps of endoscopic sinus surgery were then performed, including "uncinectomy, middle meatal antrostomy, and anterior and posterior ethmoidectomy." Depending on the specific pathology and its extent, additional procedures may have been performed on the sphenoid or frontal sinuses.

Medialization of Middle Turbinate

In group I, no fixation to nasal septum, just a small piece of merocele was put in the middle meatus for 2 days.

In group II, multiple mucosal incision (cross-hutch) were done in the anterior part of the medial surface of middle turbinate (towards the septum) using a small blade for about 3-4 mm parallel to each other with incising the adjacent part of the nasal septum to create an artificial adhesion attaching the middle turbinate to the septum preventing lateralization.

a

b

Figure 1. Iaceration of (a) Nasal Septum, (b) Middle Turbinate by Sickle Knife

In group III, the middle turbinate is sutured to the septum utilizing a 3-0 vicryl stitch. The suturing begins from the left middle turbinate, passes through the nasal septum, and next continues to the right middle turbinate. The suture is drawn forward and passed again through the nasal septum, starting from the right side and ending on the left side, at a point midway between the middle turbinate and nasal vestibule. It is next tied off on the left side of the nasal cavity.

Figure 2. Direction of The Suture of Middle Turbinate to Septum

Figure 3. Right Sided Nasal Cavity; Technique of Suturing

The middle meatal merocel packing was placed for 48 hours in all groups, and the silastic sheets were put bilaterally with nasal packing for those who underwent septal and/or inferior turbinate surgery. The nasal packing was removed after 24-48 hours, and the silastic after 5-7 days. Patients received parenteral antibiotics for 72 hours and then changed to oral for 1 week, with nasal douching and local steroid spray according to the underlying pathology.

Follow-up was done weekly during the 1st month and every 2 weeks during the 2nd month by assessing the patient symptoms (nasal obstruction, nasal discharge, facial congestion, smell perception, and headache) and nasal endoscopic findings (middle meatus patency, discharge, polyp, crustation, adhesion, and middle turbinate fixation).

Questionnaire

- Name
- Age
- Gender
- Occupation
- Residency
- Phone number
- Chief complaint
- Duration
- History of present illness
- Nasal obstruction: unilateral vs. bilateral.
- Facial congestion
- Post-nasal drip refers to the flow of mucus from the nose and throat towards the back of the throat. Anterior discharge from the nose
- Reduced olfactory perception Epistaxis
- Any other relevant symptoms
- Systemic review

- General: weight loss, pallor, anorexia...etc.
- CNS
- Cardiopulmonary
- GIT
- Past medical history: Atopy, asthma, recurrent chest infection, recurrent nasal problems, hypertension, diabetes, and immune deficiencies condition.
- Family history
- Social history: smoking, alcoholism, socioeconomic status...etc.
- Past surgical history
- Drug history

Examination

- General examination of the patient
- Nasal examination
- External nose: deviation, deformity, discoloration, ulceration...etc.
- Anterior rhinoscopy: health of mucosa, discharge, polyp, other findings...etc.
- Nasendoscope: color of mucosa, middle turbinate, middle meatal anatomy and abnormality, discharge, polyposis...etc.
- Full ENT and head and neck examination
- Computed tomography findings
- Condition of the sinuses (which sinuses are involved, unilateral vs. bilateral, complete vs. partial opacity...etc).
- Condition of ostiomeatal complex
- Structural abnormalities (septal deviation, concha bullosa, paradoxical middle turbinate...etc)
- Important anatomical consideration (cribriform plate, lamina papyracea, Onodi cell, anterior ethmoidal artery...etc)

- Other relevant pathology
- Date of ESS operation
- Surgical technique (which group of study)
- Follow up (final results after 2 months)

Symptoms Improvement

The symptoms include the presence or absence of the following (nasal obstruction, nasal discharge, facial congestion, smell perception, and headache).

Nasal Endoscopic Findings

The endoscopic findings include middle meatus patency, discharge, polyp, crustation, adhesion, and middle turbinate fixation.

Ethical Considerations

Each patient was verbally consented after the researcher explained the goal of the study. All patients had a comprehensive ENT history focused on specific sinonasal symptoms, such as nasal blockage, nasal discharge, face discomfort, and other symptoms specified in the questionnaire. A comprehensive examination of the ear, nose, and throat (including a nasal endoscopy) as well as a thorough examination of the head and neck were conducted.

Results and Discussions

The data was input and analyzed using SPSS software version 24, which employs appropriate statistical tests. The descriptive statistics included frequencies, proportions, mean, and standard deviation (SD). Before and after the operation, the average VAS scores were compared using the paired t-test, whereas Fisher's exact test was utilized to examine the frequencies or proportions. A level of significance (P value) of < 0.05 is regarded as significant, whereas a value of ≤ 0.001 is considered extremely significant. Ultimately, all the discoveries and outcomes are displayed in tables and/or figures accompanied by explanatory paragraphs as appropriate.

In this study, one hundred (55.6%) patients were males and eighty (44.4%) patients were females. Figure 4 displays the gender distribution among the studied groups.

Figure 4. Gender Distribution among the Studied Groups

The patients' ages varied from 20 to 48 years, mean \pm SD was (33.45 ± 8.95) years. The distribution of age among the studied groups is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Distribution of Ages among the Examined Groups

In a study performed by (Hegazy et al. 2015), males were 43.59% and females were 56.41%. (Weitzel and Wormald, 2008) revealed that the age varied from 14 to 56 years, with an average age of 31.8 ± 11.6 years. There was no significant variation in ages across the groups.

(Bofares, 2015) reported that his study included 60 patients aged 14 to 63 years exhibiting characteristics of chronic sinusitis .

There were no notable disparities in the age and gender distribution among the groups in this study, as well as in other studies.

Furthermore, the study aims to evaluate the patency of the middle meatus after endoscopic sinus surgery using various surgical techniques for medialization of middle turbinate to prevent it's lateralization with subsequent osteomeatal complex (OMC) obstruction and impairment of sinus drainage and ventilation, accordingly we categorized the results of surgery into 3 categories:

- Opened (OMC): full patency with complete visualization of the sinus ostia.
- Partially obliterated (OMC): It is an area of adhesion between the middle turbinate and the lateral nasal wall that is resulting in a partial obstruction of the (OMC) osteomeatal complex and sinus drainage.
- Completely obliterated (OMC): The middle turbinate is fully attached to the lateral nasal wall, resulting in total blockage of the OMC.

Initially, the patency of the middle meatus was examined endoscopically postoperatively, and a comparison was made between various surgical techniques. Regarding the results between medialization alone without fixation (group I) and medialization with fixation (groups II and III), an opened OMC was significantly observed in groups II and III, as the P value was 0.00, and a completely obliterated OMC was significantly observed in group I. There was significant improvement in middle meatal patency when medialization with the middle turbinate fixed to the nasal septum (group II & III) compared to medialization alone (group I) (Table 1).

Table1. Endoscopic Finding of Middle Meatal Patency in Relation to Type of Surgical Intervention

Middle meatal patency	No. of patients		P value
	Without fixation Group I	With fixation Group II & III	
Open	16	76	0.00
Adhesion (partial obliteration)	20	40	
Complete obliteration	24	4	
Total	60	120	

Another comparison was made between the two techniques of fixation (iatrogenic adhesion and suturing) to nasal septum in relation to the patency of middle meatus which showed significant difference (Table 2).

Table 2. Patency of Middle Meatus in Relation to Type of Fixation of Middle Turbinate

Middle meatal patency	No. of patients		P value
	iatrogenic adhesion (Group II)	suturing (Group III)	
Open	32	44	0.02
Adhesion (partial obliteration)	24	16	
Complete obliteration	4	0	
Total	60	60	

We have observed certain limitations of suturing technique, which include the following: (disruption of the stitch in one patient at day 8 post-op during removal of silastic that caused lateralization of the middle turbinate observed on subsequent follow-up, it is more time-consuming that may prolong the anesthesia time, and almost it is not easy to handle the needle near the middle turbinate).

a

b

Figure 6. Postoperative Endoscopic Findings in Suturing Technique (a) Right, and (b) Left Nasal Cavity

Hudson and Orlandi, (2013) also noted that the Endoscopic Conchopexy Suture technique has been regarded as challenging and time-consuming because it requires tying knots within the nasal cavity. However, a new method has made this operation easier by removing the need to tie knots within the nasal cavity by employing a monofilament barbed suture with pre-tied knots.

Despite these limitations, the overall results of group III is better than Group II as observed in our study and other studies (Hegazy et al. 2015; Bofares 2015; Dutton & Hinton, 2011; and González 2011).

Moreover, in this study, the predominant symptoms seen were nasal obstruction, nasal discharge, and facial pain, which were found in 140, 124, and 108 patients, respectively. Other symptoms, including smell disorders and headaches, were found in 72 and 68 patients, respectively. Post-operative improvement of these symptoms in order of sequence from higher to lower was as follows: nasal obstructions (74%), nasal discharge (74%), facial pain (70%), smell disorders (61%), and headache (53%) (Table 3).

Table 3. Preoperative Symptomatology and Postoperative Improvement of Symptoms

Groups	Symptoms									
	Nasal obstruction		Nasal discharge		Facial pain		Smell disorders		Headache	
	Pre-op	Improved post-op	Pre-op	Improved post-op	Pre-op	Improved post-op	Pre-op	Improved post-op	Pre-op	Improved post-op
Group I	40	24 (60%)	40	20 (50%)	35	15 (43%)	28	16 (57%)	24	8 (33%)
Group II	48	36 (75%)	48	40 (83%)	37	29 (78%)	24	16 (67%)	20	12 (60%)

Group III	52	44 (85%)	36	32 (89%)	36	32 (89%)	20	12 (60%)	24	16 (67%)
Total No. of patients	140	104 (74%)	124	92 (74%)	108	76 (70%)	72	44 (61%)	68	36 (53%)

By comparing the postoperative improvement of symptoms between various surgical techniques. Groups II and III, which involved medializing the middle turbinate and fixing it to the septum, demonstrated significant improvements in nasal discharge and obstruction when compared to medialization alone without fixation (group I), with a P value of less than 0.05. However, there was no significant difference in other symptoms related to the surgical techniques, as indicated in Table 4.

Table 4. Postoperative Improvement of Symptoms According to Type of Surgical Intervention

Symptoms	No. of improved patients		P value
	Without fixation Group I	With fixation Group II & III	
Nasal obstruction	24/40	80/100	0.001
Nasal discharge	20/40	72/84	0.001
Facial pain	15/35	61/73	0.1
Smell disorders	16/28	28/44	0.6
Headache	8/24	28/44	0.1

Other surgical interventions rather than anterior and posterior ethmoidectomy were done in some patients as shown in Table 5.

In this study, nasal symptoms were looked at in Table 3. It was discovered that nasal obstruction got better in groups II and III by 75% and 85%, respectively, compared to 60% in group I. In (Bofares, 2015) study the nasal obstruction was improved in group II & III by (90% & 95%) respectively and only by (55%) in group I. In the research by (Hegazy et al. 2015), all three groups exhibited significant improvement, with groups

II and III demonstrating superior outcomes (P value = 0.001) relative to group I (P value = 0.002).

Table 5. Other Surgical Interventions

Surgery	No. of patients		
	Group I	Group II	Group III
Septoplasty	56 (93%)	44 (73%)	40 (66%)
sphenoidotomy	24 (40%)	32 (53%)	44 (73%)
Frontal recess opening	12 (20%)	0 (0%)	4 (6%)

Also, the nasal discharge was improved in groups II & III by 83% & 89%, respectively, compared to 50% in group I, and there was a statistically significant difference in this improvement as the P value was 0.03. These results agree with the results reported by (Bofares, 2015) in which improvement of nasal discharge in Group I was only 45% and was 85% & 90% in groups II & III, respectively. Hegazy et al. (2015) also described improvements in group I by 63% and group II by 80%, while in group III, he recorded that all patients included in the study were free from nasal discharge postoperatively (i.e., 100%).

In addition, facial pain (congestion) was significantly improved in groups II & III by 78% & 89%, respectively, compared to 43% in group I, and the P value was 0.03. Bofares (2015) stated that group I showed improvement in only 45% compared to 85% & 95% in groups II & III, respectively. Hegazy et al. (2015) indicated that there was a statistically significant improvement in facial congestion, with P values of 0.002 for group I, 0.001 for group II, and 0.0007 for group III.

On the other hand, postoperatively, there was minimal variation in smell perception among the three groups, with group I experiencing a 57% improvement, group II a 67% improvement, and group III a 60% improvement. Bofares (2015) showed better improvements regarding smell perception by 80% and 90% in groups II and III, respectively, compared to only 45% in group I. Hegazy et al. (2015) described improvement in all three groups, but it was not significant ($P = 0.04$).

Furthermore, in group I, postoperative headache improvement was 33%; in group II, it was 60%, and in group III, it was 67%. Bofares (2015) conducted that the percentage of participants in group I was 45%, while group II and group III had 80% and 90% of participants, respectively.

Conclusion

The method of medializing the middle turbinate and securing it to the nasal septum is used in endoscopic sinus surgery to improve the patency of the middle meatus. This technique promotes effective drainage, healing of the nasal mucosa, proper ventilation, and allows for long-term monitoring and suction clearance. Additionally, it improves access for topical medication to reach the sinuses. Although it has its limits, the suturing method of the middle turbinate (conchopexy) is a successful technique for preventing lateralization of the middle turbinate. This method has been found to have superior overall outcomes compared to the iatrogenic adhesion technique (Bolgerization).

Recommendation

More research needs to be done on other surgical methods for medializing the middle turbinate, like the septal flap, glue adhesion, and silastic support. Additionally, a larger number of patients and a longer duration of study are necessary.

References

- Banfield, G. K., & McCombe, A. (1999). Partial resection of the middle turbinate at functional endoscopic sinus surgery. *Journal of the Royal Army Medical Corps*, 145(1), 18–19. <https://doi.org/10.1136/jramc-145-01-05>
- Bhalla, R. K., Kaushik, V., & De Carpentier, J. (2005). Conchopexy suture to prevent middle turbinate lateralisation and septal haematoma after endoscopic sinus surgery. *Rhinology*, 43(2), 143–145.
- Bofares, K. M. (2015). Effect of middle turbinate intervention on outcomes of middle meatal endoscopic surgery. *International Journal of Otorhinolaryngology*, 1(2), 13–19. <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.ij.o.20150102.11>
- Chen, W., Wang, Y., Bi, Y., & Chen, W. (2015). Turbinate-septal suture for middle turbinate medialization: A prospective randomized trial. *Laryngoscope*, 125(1), 33–35. <https://doi.org/10.1002/lary.24820>
- Dutton, J. M., & Hinton, M. J. (2011). Middle turbinate suture conchopexy during endoscopic sinus surgery does not impair olfaction. *American Journal of Rhinology & Allergy*, 25(2), 125–127. <https://doi.org/10.2500/ajra.2011.25.3560>
- González, P. G. C. A., & Morales, C. G. M. (2011). Middle turbinate medialization technique in nasal endoscopic surgery. *Otorrinolaringología*, 56(3).
- Hegazy, M. A., Shawky, A., El Fouly, M. S., & El Kabani, A. (2015). Conchopexy of middle turbinate versus bolgarization in endoscopic sinus surgery. *Egyptian Journal of Otolaryngology*, 31, 219–223.
- Hewitt, K. M., & Orlandi, R. R. (2008). Suture medialization of the middle turbinate during endoscopic sinus surgery. *Ear, Nose & Throat Journal*, 87(12), E11.
- Hudson, S., & Orlandi, R. (2013). Knot-free suture medialization of the middle turbinate.

International Forum of Allergy & Rhinology, 3(10), 855–856. <https://doi.org/10.1002/alr.21194>

Lal, D., & Stankiewicz, J. A. (2010). Primary sinus surgery. In *Cummings Otolaryngology: Head and Neck Surgery* (5th ed., pp. 739–758). <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-323-05283-2.00052-5>

Lee, M. R., & Marple, B. F. (2011). Middle turbinate medialization for improved access

during endoscopic sinus surgery. *International Forum of Allergy & Rhinology*, 1(3), 187–190. <https://doi.org/10.1002/alr.20013>

Weitzel, E. K., & Wormald, P. J. (2008). A scientific review of middle meatal packing/stents. *American Journal of Rhinology*, 22(3), 302–307. <https://doi.org/10.2500/ajr.2008.22.3171>